

TRANSIENT DUAL-PHASE VOID PREDICTION IN MICROSCOPIC YARN MODELS WITH OPENFOAM

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ABSTRACT

Permeability measurements and analytical solutions for permeability prediction in the area of endless fiber reinforced plastics have a long history and are used as input for state of the art FEM mold filling simulations. As published in the third permeability benchmark, experimental measurement of permeability still shows big variations (29 - 38 %) depending on different measurement techniques, test rigs and test procedures [1]. It was shown that numerical solutions can support these results by modelling the fiber architecture at microscopic and mesoscopic scale [2-5]. These approaches also proved to be capable of taking into consideration the dual-scale effect of intra- and inter-yarn flow in endless fiber textiles [6].

In this study, the ability of numerical approaches to predict void formation and void transport on microscopic scale will be shown. Afterwards, we will compare the numerical microscopic prediction with published experimental results. Additionally, we will present an approach to upscale the microscopic void volume content to a simulation of mesoscopic textile impregnation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today, lightweight structures made of fibre-reinforced plastics are used in many areas of the mobility sector. To reduce waste, save resources and lower the costs as well as the manufacturing cycles, we have to understand the impregnation mechanism taking place during the infiltration of fibre-reinforced plastics. Otherwise, we will have to handle dry spots, racetracks, high void contents, fibre washing, etc. by trial-and-error production. This is inefficient and leads to high costs, wasting resources and long development phases.

An unsolved problem in the production of fibre-reinforced plastics is the generation, transportation and occurrence of high void contents in areas of critical stresses. If we could predict the void content of a textile architecture during infiltration and consider it in the stiffness prediction, our results would be closer to reality and could improve the prediction of fatigue behaviour of fibre-reinforced plastics.

Experimental investigations on this topic by Ruiz et al. [7] used a unidirectional glass fibre fabric to monitor the voids during infiltration. They found that for different velocities of the flow front different amounts of voids were captured in the textile. In addition, they observed that these voids have different sizes depending on the flow front velocity. Their conclusion was that for higher flow front velocities microscopic voids (inside the yarns; intra-yarn) and for slower velocities macroscopic voids (outside the yarns; inter-yarn) would be generated (cf. Figure 1).

They also proposed an optimal capillary number corresponding to the minimum void volume content of 0 %, which derives from their model and experiments with single unidirectional textile preforms. Other researchers like Gueroult et al. [8] used electric conductivity sensors to measure the void content during infiltration and compared them to their proposed model. Nevertheless, they found a minimum void volume content of 2 % in their measurements, which could be due to the stacking of multiple layers or measurement inaccuracies.

Figure 1: The proposed void content model by Ruiz et al. [7]

In order to proof these equations and measurements as well as to understand what happens in the fabric during the infiltration, we simulate the impregnation of microscopic yarn models. To predict micro voids, we simulate the infiltration with a transient dual-phase solver in OpenFOAM. Afterwards we analyse the void contents and compare them to the experimental approaches. The results will be transferred to first simplified mesoscopic void simulations to address the dual-scale effect as well as dual-phase phenomena (microscopic and macroscopic void generation) in fibre textiles.

2 SIMULATION SET-UP

To predict the formation of voids and their transport in microscopic yarn models, we generate random positioned fiber cross sections within a certain domain, using an in-house pre-processing tool. The algorithm we use to randomize the distribution of the filaments is the initial-periodic-shaking algorithm by G. Catalanotti [9].

Hereby, we generate three different fiber volume contents (FVC: 37 %, 45 % and 58 %) to simulate the void formation and the void volume content (VVC) in dependence with the fiber volume content. The dimensions of the models are $174 \times 174 \mu\text{m}$ with a filament diameter of $d_f = 7 \mu\text{m}$ and up to 459 filaments, represented by white circles within the domain (cf. Figure 2).

Figure 2: Microscopic yarn model and defined boundary patches

The generated microscopic filament models are transferred to a CFD tool (OpenFOAM) using a transient dual-phase solver (interFoam) to describe the fluid and the gas phase. In this study, two-dimensional cross sections of yarns are modelled, simulated and analysed as representative volume elements (RVE). Every simulation model consists out of four boundary faces (inlet, outlet and two walls) (cf. Figure 2). The faces in z -direction are set empty and have no influence on the numerical results. Filament boundaries are set to wall condition.

For the flow simulation inside the microscopic yarn models, a dynamic viscosity of $\eta_f = 109$ mPas and a density of $\rho_f = 1226$ kg/m³ are used for the fluid phase (e.g. Glycerol 85 %). For the gas phase, we use a density of $\rho_g = 1.225$ kg/m³ and a dynamic viscosity of $\eta_g = 0.0171$ mPas (e.g. Air). The contact angle was set to $\theta = 52.96^\circ$ and the surface tension was defined to $\gamma = 65.19$ mN/m. We investigated these values from measurements of Glycerol 85 % [6]. To initiate a flow within the models, a pressure gradient between inlet and outlet is set. It is varied depending on the modified capillary number Ca^* and the FVC (cf. Table 1). The modified capillary number Ca^* is defined as,

$$Ca^* = \frac{\eta v}{\gamma \cos \theta} \quad (1)$$

with v the velocity of the fluid, γ the surface tension and θ the contact angle between the fluid phase and the filaments [7].

Inlet pressure [bar]	Ca^* -value [-]
0.5	0.0008
5	0.012
50	0.126
150	0.366
250	0.624
750	1.851

Table 1: Inlet pressure at FVG = 45 % and corresponding Ca^* -value

3 RESULTS

3.1 Microscopic void simulation

Looking at Figure 3, we see a flow simulation within a microscopic yarn model. The fluid is flowing from the left boundary (inlet) to the right boundary (outlet). Completely filled areas with pure fluid phase are coloured red, whereas pure gas phase areas are coloured blue. Partly filled areas, that have contents of fluid and gas phase, are smeared coloured between orange and light blue.

We observe that certain filament arrangements and fabric architectures generate voids inside the yarn through capturing parts of the gas phase (cf. Figure 3).

Looking at the void transport (gas phase transport) in the dashed boxes in Figure 4 ($t = 0.016$ s), we see that during the infiltration process the gas phase is transported to the outlet through a flow channel. This flow channel is visualized by a smeared colour stream to the right border of the Figure. If the reservoir of the gas phase in an area vanishes (cf. Figure 4, $t = 0.028$ s), the smeared flow channel with the origin in that area dilutes.

In addition, looking at the flow vectors we see that voids coincident with areas of slow or none velocity, where areas with high velocity show less voids or a transport of fluid and gas phase to the outlet, indicated by smeared flow channels (cf. Figure 5).

To analyse the void volume content we used an in-house Matlab[®] code, based on a greyscale algorithm. Thus, it was possible to examine simulation results and experimental cut section images, similarly. To visualize the VVC, we generate a binary plot of the voids of the model (cf. Figure 6). Results for the simulation model are given as a parameter set of fiber volume content and void volume content in Table 2.

Figure 3: Microscopic dual phase yarn simulation
(gas phase = blue; fluid phase = red)

Figure 4: Detailed view on the gas phase transport (gas phase = blue; fluid phase = red)

Comparing the fiber volume content (FVC) of the post processing step to the originally simulation model, we can prove that the defined FVC was detected. To proof the void volume content (VVC) more precisely, a better resolution of phases is necessary, especially in zones of combined gas and fluid phases.

Figure 5: Detailed view on velocity vectors (grey scale) in a microscopic yarn simulation with two phases (gas phase = blue; fluid phase = red)

	Grey scale value [-]	Content [%]
Filament (FVC)	160-255	0.452
Fluid phase	56-159	0.526
Gas phase (VVC)	0-55	0.022

Table 2: Post processing parameter for determination of model contents

Figure 6: Binary display of voids out of a microscopic yarn simulation (white = voids; black = fluid and filaments)

3.2 Comparison of microscopic simulations to experimental measurements

We visualize the simulated void content of the microscopic simulations versus the calculated modified capillary number Ca^* . Looking at the Results in Fig. 7, we obtain that microscopic voids are generated within the yarn, independently from the Ca^* -value. What we also see is that the microscopic void content is decreasing from $Ca^* = 0.001$ to a value between $Ca^* = 0.1$ and $Ca^* = 1$. Afterwards it is increasing to a value between $Ca^* = 1$ and $Ca^* = 1.9$. We did not simulate with higher Ca^* -values, as compressible effects in the gas phase could not be considered with the interFoam solver.

Figure 7: Simulated void volume content against the modified capillary number Ca^* including experimental measurements of Ruiz et al., Gueroult et al. and DeValve et al.

Examining the minimum void contents for the simulation with FVCs of 37 %, 45 % and 58 % (cf. Figure 7); we recognize a minimum void content of 1.55 %, 1.2 % and 2.28 %. This leads to the assumption that there is an optimum for the microscopic void content for every specific filament arrangement. Although, the minimum VVC is at a FVC of 45 %, it seems that there is a trend to higher microscopic void contents with larger FVCs. Thinking about very dense packed yarns, we could imagine that the fluid flow is weaker inside the yarn and more voids are generated or less voids are transported to the outlet.

In addition, looking at the void content values and adding a best fit line for the different simulations, we detect a slightly higher slope for microscopic void contents below the optimum capillary number for each simulation. This agrees to experimental studies of Ruiz et al. [7] and Gueroult et al. [8].

Continuing, we see that the simulations show less void content and mellow slopes. What we have to point out here is that only the microscopic void content within the yarn is simulated and that the slopes of Ruiz et al. and Gueroult et al. are also including mesoscopic and macroscopic inter-yarn voids. Nevertheless, focusing on the minimum void content, we could not simulate a void volume content of 0 % as Ruiz et al. found, but we are in good agreement with the minimum void content of Gueroult et al. between 1.55 % and 2.5 % and experimental measurements by DeValve et al. [10] between 1 % and 2.5 %.

3.3 Upscaling the void content to mesoscopic textile simulation

In Figure 8, we simulate a two-dimensional mesoscopic impregnation of a fiber yarn cross section including a porous zone within the yarn. As the fluid is flowing around the porous yarn, it capsules a gas phase within the yarn. This represents the intra-yarn void content that we have already simulated at microscopic scale. After that, a separation of the gas phase from intra-yarn to inter-yarn flow occurs and the fluid flow transports the generated voids to the outlet.

Using this method, we assume that there is a potential to consider voids in a mesoscopic simulation, which can improve our understanding of void formation and void transport in fiber textile architectures. Nevertheless, a full three-dimensional transient dual-phase simulation of large textile structures would be too ambitious now, but the approach could be suitable for simulating textiles at mesoscopic unit cell level.

Figure 8: Mesoscopic dual-phase simulation of a fluid flow around a porous yarn cross section (gas phase = blue; fluid phase = red)

4 CONCLUSION

We showed that microscopic flow simulation could predict void formation, void transport and the void volume content inside a microscopic yarn model, using a dual-phase solver in OpenFOAM.

Compared to the experimental results of Ruiz et al. [7] we could not simulate a void volume content of 0 %. Relating to the experimental results of Gueroult et al. [8] and DeValve et al. [10], the minimal void content is in good agreement with the predicted results of this study.

The results are looking promising although the void contents for microscopic yarn simulations are lower and the minima are at higher flow front velocities, compared to published experimental results. What we observed in simulation is that there is also a minimum for microscopic void formation without the existence of any mesoscopic or macroscopic voids and that there is a logarithmic correlation between void volume content and flow front velocity.

Using the void content of a microscopic simulated yarn, we can upscale this parameter to simulate voids in mesoscopic textile architectures. Here we could understand more about void formation and void transport in dual-scale mesoscopic simulations. Additionally, we can include these results in our single-phase textile simulations by defining the porosity of the yarn with respect to the simulated microscopic void content.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. May, A. Aktas, S. G. Advani et al. In-Plane Permeability Characterization of Engineering Textiles Based On Radial Flow Experiments: A Benchmark Exercise. In: *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2019. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa. 2019.03.006.
- [2] M. Engelfried, L. Antonin Mavoungou, I. Verspohl, P. Böhler, P. Middendorf. Generating Representative Volume Elements of Yarns with Non-Circular Filaments' Cross-Sections. 14th International Conference on Flow Processes in Composite Materials, Luleå, Sweden, 2018
- [3] J. Dittmann, S. Hügle, P. Seif, L. Kauffmann and P. Middendorf. Permeability Prediction Using Porous Yarns in a Dual-Scale Simulation with OpenFOAM. 21th International Conference on Composite Materials, Xi'an, China, 2017.
- [4] E. Swery, R. Meier, S. V. Lomov, C. Hahn, P. Kelly and I. Straumit. Verification of FlowTex Solver using Ansys CFX; Examining the Permeability Prediction Method on a Range of Textile Architecture Models, in European Conference On Composite Materials, Seville, Spain, 2014.
- [5] X. Zeng, A. Endruweit, L. P. Brown and A. C. Long. Numerical prediction of in-plane permeability for multilayer woven fabrics with manufacture-induced deformation, *Composites: Part A*, 77, p. 266–274, 2015.
- [6] J. Dittmann, P. Middendorf. Experimental Validation of Numerical Dual-Scale Permeability Prediction. 14th International Conference on Flow Processes in Composite Materials, Luleå, Sweden, 2018
- [7] E. Ruiz, V. Achim, S. Soukane, F. Trochu and J. Bréard. Optimization of injection flow rate to minimize micro/macro-voids formation in resin transfer molded composites. *Composites science and technology*, 2006, 66(3-4), 475-486.
- [8] S. Gueroult, A. Lebel-Lavacry, C. H. Park, L. Bizet, A. Saouab, J. Bréard. Analytical modeling and in situ measurement of void formation in liquid composite molding processes. *Advanced Composite Materials*, 23(1), 31-42, 2014.
- [9] G. Catalanotti. On the generation of RVE-based models of composites reinforced with long fibres or spherical particles. *Composite Structures*, 138, 84-95, 2016.
- [10] C. DeValve and R. Pitchumani. Simulation of void formation in liquid composite molding processes. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2013, 51, 22-32.